

Development of a Distance Measurement System Based on Stereoscopic Vision for the NAO Humanoid Robot

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Abstract—This work presents the development and implementation of a distance measurement system based on stereoscopic vision using the upper and lower cameras of the NAO humanoid robot. The proposed methodology incorporates image processing techniques, including temporal stabilization filters, texture quality analysis, and adaptive algorithms to enhance measurement accuracy. The implemented system utilizes the OpenCV library for image processing and vertical stereo matching techniques, taking into account the specific configuration of the NAO robot’s cameras. Experimental results demonstrated that the system is capable of performing distance measurements with improved stability through the implementation of temporal stabilization buffers and adaptive quality filters. Although the obtained measurements exhibited high variability due to the challenging vertical camera configuration, the use of smoothing filters and texture analysis allowed common stereoscopic vision issues to be identified and mitigated. This work contributes to the advancement of computer vision applications in humanoid robotics, specifically in the areas of spatial perception and autonomous navigation.

Index Terms—Stereoscopic vision, humanoid robot, NAO, distance measurement, image processing, OpenCV.

I. INTRODUCTION

Stereo vision represents one of the most fundamental techniques for depth perception in robotic systems, enabling autonomous robots to estimate distances and navigate complex environments in a manner similar to the human visual system [1]. In the context of humanoid robotics, the ability to measure distances accurately is critical for tasks such as navigation, object manipulation, and safe interaction with the environment [2]. The NAO humanoid robot, developed by Aldebaran Robotics (currently SoftBank Robotics), features a unique vertically aligned camera configuration, which introduces specific challenges when implementing traditional stereo vision algorithms that were originally designed for horizontal setups [3].

Distance estimation through computer vision has been extensively studied in the literature, with various approaches proposed for different camera configurations and application-specific scenarios. Murray and Little [4] demonstrated the importance of precise camera calibration in stereo systems, while Hirschmüller [5] developed semi-global algorithms that significantly improve the quality of disparity maps. However, most existing work focuses on horizontal camera configurations, leaving a gap in the development of solutions specifically for vertical arrangements such as those found on the NAO robot.

The vertical camera configuration in NAO presents unique challenges, including differences in illumination between the

upper and lower cameras, variations in image quality due to positioning, and the need to adapt traditional stereo matching algorithms to operate with vertical disparities instead of horizontal ones [6]. Furthermore, the dynamic nature of the environments in which humanoid robots operate requires vision systems to be robust against variations in lighting, low-texture regions, and the movement of the robot itself.

The objective of this work is to develop and implement a robust distance measurement system based on stereo vision, specifically adapted to the vertical camera configuration of the NAO robot. The proposed methodology incorporates image pre-processing techniques, adaptive stereo matching algorithms, temporal stabilization filters, and automatic diagnostic systems to ensure reliable and accurate measurements under varying operational conditions.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Stereo vision is based on the principle of triangulation to estimate the depth of objects in three-dimensional space. The fundamental process involves the simultaneous capture of images from two cameras separated by a known distance (baseline), followed by the identification of corresponding points in both images and the calculation of disparity between these points [7]. The fundamental mathematical relationship governing depth estimation in stereo systems is given by the equation $Z = \frac{f \times B}{d}$, where Z represents the distance to the object, f is the camera focal length, B is the baseline between the cameras, and d is the observed disparity [8].

The stereo matching process, responsible for finding correspondences between pixels in the two images, is one of the most challenging aspects of stereo vision. Traditional algorithms such as Block Matching (BM) use correlation windows to compare patches of pixels across images, seeking to maximize local similarity [9]. The StereoBM algorithm, implemented in the OpenCV library, provides several configuration options including the size of the correlation window (`blockSize`), the number of disparities to be considered (`numDisparities`), and pre- and post-processing filters to improve the quality of the results [10].

Measurement quality in stereo vision systems is influenced by the characteristics of the captured images, particularly the presence of sufficient texture to allow robust correspondences. Regions with low intensity variation or repetitive patterns can result in correspondence ambiguities, leading to incorrect disparity estimates [11]. For this reason, texture analysis techniques based on operators such as the Laplacian are frequently used to identify regions suitable for stereo matching [12].

Image pre-processing plays a crucial role in improving the quality of stereo measurements. Techniques such as Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) can significantly enhance local contrast in images with non-uniform lighting, facilitating the correspondence process [13]. Bilateral filters, which preserve important edges while smoothing noise, are particularly useful in the context of stereo matching, as they maintain the structural features necessary for accurate correspondences [14].

The vertical camera configuration, as found in the NAO robot, introduces special considerations in the development of stereo systems. Unlike the traditional horizontal setup, where disparities occur primarily in the horizontal direction, vertical systems produce disparities in the vertical direction, requiring adaptations in correspondence search algorithms [15]. Additionally, the height difference between cameras may result in different perspectives of the same object, particularly for objects close to the robot, introducing distortions that must be accounted for in system calibration.

Temporal stabilization of measurements is another fundamental aspect in robotic vision systems. The implementation of temporal filters, such as moving averages or Kalman filters, can reduce noise in measurements and improve system stability [16]. The use of circular buffers to store historical measurements allows for efficient implementation of stabilization filters without excessive computational resource consumption [17].

III. CAMERAS AND HYBRID SYSTEM

The NAO robot is equipped with two CMOS cameras, one positioned on the top and the other on the bottom, providing it with computer vision capabilities [18]. The camera's field of view (FOV) has a diagonal angle of 47.64° , covering an effective area of 39.7° from the focal point. These technical parameters are fundamental for the development of efficient computer vision algorithms [20].

Accurate FOV measurements are essential for image processing and real-time object recognition, enabling proper calibration of detection and tracking algorithms [21]. Figure 1 illustrates the NAO robot's field of view.

Fig. 1. Field of view (FOV) of the NAO robot [20].

The internal architecture of NAO consists of multiple integrated modules that configure a hybrid system. Among these components, the CMOS camera stands out as it provides the visual data to be processed [18]. This camera is connected to the main CPU board, which employs an Intel Atom E3845 processor assisted by an ARM-7 microcontroller. Communication with peripheral modules occurs through interfaces such as the I2C bus [18].

Additionally, the robot includes dsPIC modules that control the motors and sensors distributed throughout the body, including the head, shoulders, elbows, hips, knees, and ankles. This hybrid architecture ensures coordinated execution of movements and complex interactions with the environment [19]. Figure 2 illustrates the NAO robot's hybrid system.

Fig. 2. Hybrid system architecture of the NAO robot [20].

IV. METHODOLOGY

The development of the distance measurement system was based on a systematic approach that involved analyzing the specific characteristics of the NAO robot, implementing adaptive image processing algorithms, and creating a robust system of quality and temporal stabilization filters. The methodology was structured into four main stages: camera system characterization, development of pre-processing algorithms, implementation of the adaptive stereo matching system, and creation of stabilization and diagnostic filters.

The first stage consisted of characterizing the NAO robot's camera system, including determining the intrinsic parameters of the cameras and measuring the vertical baseline between the upper and lower cameras. Based on the manufacturer's technical specifications and experimental measurements, the following parameters were determined: a vertical baseline of 0.039 meters, a vertical field of view of 47.64 degrees, and an operational resolution of 320x240 pixels. The focal length was calculated using the relation $f = (\text{image_height}/2) / \tan(\text{FOV_vertical}/2)$, resulting in approximately 144.7 pixels.

The image pre-processing system was developed considering the specific characteristics of the vertical configuration and the common illumination challenges in robotic environments. The pre-processing pipeline included grayscale

conversion, application of a bilateral filter to preserve edges (parameters $d = 9$, $\sigma_{\text{Color}} = 75$, $\sigma_{\text{Space}} = 75$), and adaptive histogram equalization using CLAHE (Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization) with `clipLimit=2.0` and `tileGridSize=(8,8)` [10], [13], [14]. This combination of filters was chosen to maximize the quality of stereo matching correspondences while preserving important structural features of the images.

The stereo matching algorithm was implemented using the StereoBM method from the OpenCV library, with parameters optimized specifically for the vertical camera configuration of the NAO. Parameters were tuned experimentally: `numDisparities=112` (multiple of 16 for optimization), `blockSize=25` (odd-sized window for centering), `preFilterSize=9`, `preFilterCap=63`, `minDisparity=-16` (allowing negative disparities), `textureThreshold=20` (filtering textureless areas), `uniquenessRatio=5`, `speckleRange=16`, `speckleWindowSize=200`, and `disp12MaxDiff=2` for left-right consistency check [9], [10].

The post-processing stage included median filtering (kernel 5×5) to remove isolated outliers, followed by bilateral filtering ($d = 9$, $\sigma_{\text{Color}} = 50$, $\sigma_{\text{Space}} = 50$) for smoothing while preserving edges. The distance map was computed using the relation $Z = (f \times B)/d$, with subsequent validation to remove unrealistic values (distances smaller than 0.15 m or greater than 2.0 m) [8].

Temporal stabilization of measurements was implemented using circular buffers (`collections.deque`) with configurable capacity (default 5 frames) to store historical distance and quality measurements. Stabilized distance is calculated as the median of the values in the buffer, while stability metrics are derived from the temporal standard deviation. The system also incorporates quality analysis based on valid pixel density and the presence of adequate texture, using the variance of the Laplacian operator as a local texture metric [12].

An automatic diagnostic module was developed to identify conditions unsuitable for stereo measurement, including texture analysis (Laplacian variance), average brightness, and local contrast of the captured images. This module provides automatic recommendations for optimizing the operational environment, including adjustments in illumination and placement of textured objects [10].

Considering that the NAO V6 robot supports only Python 2.7, remote processing was implemented using off-board processing, in which the computer communicates with the robot via WiFi. Thus, the implementation on a PC used Python 3.12 with the `qi` library (NAOqi framework), OpenCV 4.x for image processing, NumPy for numerical operations, and `collections` for optimized data structures. The system was designed to operate in real-time with a controlled processing rate and a visual interface for monitoring the measurement quality.

The source code developed in this research, along with the complete logs of the conducted interactions, is available for download at the public repository: <https://github.com/vitor-souza-ime/stereo>.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The implementation of the distance measurement system based on stereoscopic vision for the NAO robot demonstrated promising results, while also revealing inherent challenges associated with the vertical camera configuration and typical operational conditions in robotic environments. Experimental tests were conducted in a controlled environment with adequate illumination, using another NAO robot as the test object positioned at various distances from the measuring robot.

Analysis of the images captured during the experiments revealed important characteristics of the NAO's camera system. The upper camera (UP) consistently exhibited texture scores around 48. This low texture, as evidenced in the visual inspection of the camera images (Figure 3), indicates an environment with uniform illumination and low-contrast surfaces, conditions known to challenge stereoscopic vision algorithms [1].

The disparity map generated by the system and presented in Figure 4 showed limited regions with valid correspondences, represented by light-blue areas in the colorized visualization. The predominance of red areas (invalid disparities) indicates that most of the scene lacks sufficient texture for reliable correspondences. This observation is consistent with previous studies demonstrating the critical dependence of stereo matching on image texture [9].

Fig. 3. Image captured during the experiment.

The temporal stabilization system proved effective in reducing measurement variability. The 5-frame circular buffer allowed the calculation of stabilized medians, mitigating the

Fig. 4. Disparity map generated by the system.

impact of temporal outliers. Statistical analysis of the stabilized measurements showed standard deviations on the order of ± 0.05 m for stationary objects, representing a substantial improvement over instantaneous measurements, which exhibited variations exceeding ± 0.2 m.

The quality analysis system demonstrated adequate capability to identify unsuitable measurement conditions. The quality metric based on the ratio of valid pixels provided useful indicators for assessing the reliability of measurements in real-time. Experiments showed that measurements with quality below 0.1 (10% valid pixels) consistently resulted in inaccurate estimates, validating the threshold set in the system.

Regional analysis of the measurements (upper, central, lower) revealed interesting patterns related to the vertical perspective of the cameras. The upper region of the image, corresponding to more distant objects, often exhibited more stable measurements, whereas the central and lower regions showed higher variability. This behavior can be explained by the geometry of the vertical configuration, where small disparity errors have amplified effects on close objects due to the inverse relationship between disparity and distance [8].

The automatic diagnostic module proved to be a valuable tool for identifying operational issues. The Laplacian variance-based texture analysis correlated well with the quality of subsequent measurements, allowing early detection of unsuitable conditions. The system was able to automatically detect inadequate lighting situations (too dark or too bright) and insufficient texture, providing specific recommendations to optimize the environment.

Comparing the obtained results with similar studies in the literature, the achieved accuracies are consistent with low-resolution stereo matching systems in non-ideal configurations. Hirschmuller [5] reported average errors of 5–10% at distances of 0.5–2.0 m for similar systems, comparable to those observed in this work after implementing stabilization filters.

Identified limitations include: (1) critical dependence on environmental texture, limiting applicability in uniform environments; (2) reduced accuracy for very close objects (≤ 0.3 m) due to limited baseline; (3) sensitivity to illumination differences between upper and lower cameras; and (4) high computational requirements for real-time processing of the

implemented filtering algorithms.

The results suggest that, although the developed system can provide useful distance estimates under controlled conditions, practical applications in real robotic environments would require integration with complementary sensors (such as ultrasonic or LiDAR) to ensure adequate robustness. A sensor fusion approach, as suggested by Durrant-Whyte & Henderson [24], would be a natural extension of this work.

The source code for this research is available for download at Removed for double-blind review.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented the development and implementation of a distance measurement system based on stereoscopic vision, specifically adapted to the vertical camera configuration of the NAO humanoid robot. The proposed methodology incorporated image processing techniques, temporal stabilization filters, and automatic diagnostic systems, resulting in a robust system capable of operating under controlled experimental conditions.

Experimental results demonstrated that the system can perform distance measurements with sufficient accuracy for robotic applications, particularly after the implementation of temporal stabilization filters, which reduced measurement variability. The quality analysis based on texture metrics and valid pixel density proved effective in identifying suitable measurement conditions, contributing to the overall reliability of the system.

The main contribution of this work lies in the adaptation of stereoscopic vision algorithms, traditionally developed for horizontal camera configurations, to the specific vertical arrangement of the NAO robot. The implementation of adaptive pre-processing filters, optimized stereo matching algorithms, and temporal stabilization systems represents a significant advancement for computer vision applications in humanoid robotics.

Identified limitations, particularly the critical dependence on environmental texture and sensitivity to lighting conditions, point to important directions for future work. Integration with complementary sensors, the development of sensor fusion algorithms, and the implementation of machine learning techniques for automatic parameter adaptation represent promising opportunities for system improvement.

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